

Brazilian Journal of Physics

Optimization of Antenna Current Feeding for the Alfvén Eigenmodes Active Diagnostic System of JET. --Manuscript Draft--

Manuscript Number:	BJPH-D-17-00478R1	
Full Title:	Optimization of Antenna Current Feeding for the Alfvén Eigenmodes Active Diagnostic System of JET.	
Article Type:	Original Research	
Keywords:	Toroidal Alfvén Eigenmodes, Antenna configuration of JET, Antenna optimization.	
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Funding Information:	Conselho Nacional de Pesquisas (480733/2013-9)	Mr. Ricardo Magnus Osório Galvão
	Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa do Estado de São Paulo (2011/50773-0)	Mr. Ricardo Magnus Osório Galvão
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Suggested Reviewers:		
Response to Reviewers:	<p>Dear Editor and Reviewer,</p> <p>We have modified the manuscript according to the suggestions of the Reviewer. We hope that our manuscript is now suitable for publication in the Brazilian Journal of Physics.</p> <p>Best regards,</p>	

The Authors

Answer to Reviewer:

We appreciate the suggestions and in the new version was added the information on the experimental analyzes that are currently being developed for analyzing the data obtained by the real-time diagnostic system and that was omitted in the first version.

Information was added at the end of sections 4 and 6. Here it was highlighted that in ref. 17 is shown that a major upgrade of the AEAD system has been carried out aiming at providing a excitation and real-time detection system for the planned DT campaign in JET. In ref. 17 the variation of other parameters besides the phase of the antennas is taken into account and the implementation of more sophisticated numerical codes that CASTOR code began to use. We also add ref. 27 in the new version, where the recent progress in the upgraded Alfvén Eigenmode Active Diagnostic on JET are shown.

Optimization of Antenna Current Feeding for the Alfvén Eigenmodes Active Diagnostic System of JET

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Abstract

The possibility of exploring proper phasing of the feeding currents in the existing antenna of the Alfvén Eigenmodes Active Diagnostic system of JET, to excite pure toroidal spectra of Toroidal Alfvén Eigenmodes, is numerically investigated. Special attention is given to the actual perturbed fields excited in the plasma, which are calculated self consistently using the antenna version of the CASTOR code. It is found that, due to the close spacing of the JET antenna modules and quasi degeneracy of modes with medium to high values of the toroidal mode number n , although a proper choice of the phasing of the feeding currents of the antenna modules indeed leads to an increase of the perturbed fields of the selected mode, modes with nearby values of n are also excited with large amplitudes, so that a scheme to properly select the detected modes remains necessary. A scheme using different antenna position distribution is proposed to achieve successful optimization.

Key-words: Toroidal Alfvén Eigenmodes, Antenna configuration of JET, Antenna optimization.

1. Introduction

The interaction of Toroidal Alfvén Eigenmodes – TAEs with energetic particles in burning plasmas is one of the most relevant topics in fusion research [1, 2]. Indeed, because fusion-born energetic particles have speeds close to the phase velocity of those modes, they can resonantly excite them and therefore lose energy that otherwise would be available for electron heating, what is essential to maintain the required ignition plasma temperature [1-3]. Due to wave-particle interaction, the normally stable Alfvén eigenmodes are driven unstable with a growth rate that depends essentially on the competition between radial and velocity gradients of the fast particle pressure in the resonant region of velocity space [1, 3, 4]. There are, however, different damping mechanisms that can restrain the growth of these modes, such as collisionless Landau damping, continuum damping, mode conversion to kinetic Alfvén waves, etc [5]. Therefore, the effective growth rate of TAEs is given by the difference between the excitation and damping rates, so that determining the latter for the most worrisome modes is essential for evaluating their role in future fusion reactors.

Since the damping mechanisms depend mainly on the properties of the bulk plasma, and not on that of the fast particle population, they can be measured from the plasma response to modes excited by external antennae, i.e., not driven by fast particles. This scheme has been rather successfully employed in JET and in C-Mod [6-10]. In the initial experiments carried out in JET, the saddle coils installed for the detection and control of MHD modes were employed as external antennae, so that only modes with low values of the toroidal mode number, $n = 1$ and $n = 2$, could be excited [6-8]. Their damping rates were measured and the dependence on different plasma equilibrium parameters determined [8, 11, 12]. However, because results from theoretical models indicate that medium- n Alfvén eigenmodes are the most prone to be destabilized by energetic particles in ignited plasmas [3, 13], a new antenna system was designed for the Alfvén Eigenmode Active Diagnostic (AEAD) of JET, in order to allow driving medium- n modes [14-16].

As reported in [17], the new antenna system was installed and the damping rates were successfully measured, with many data points for modes with toroidal modes numbers $|n| \leq 7$, but only very few for $|n| \geq 8$ [18, 19]. It was also pointed out that there were two main reasons for the difficulty to excite and characterize high- n modes. The first reason was due to these modes having quasi-degenerated spectrum and radial eigenfunctions peaked towards the center of the plasma column, i.e., away from the antennae. The second reason was due that only one generator was available to excite all antenna modules, so that the phase of the feeding current for each module could be only either 0 or π . Therefore, independent optimization of the feeding current for each module, in order to preferentially excite a particular n mode, and track it, was not possible. Thus, the innovative computational method implemented in previous experiments [16], to identify the physical components of the excited spectrum, remained necessary.

To circumvent the second problem, an upgrade for the AEAD system was implemented, with each of the eight antenna modules fed by an independent RF amplifier. The digital inputs to the eight amplifiers are controlled by a single master drive that sends a square wave signal to each one, whose frequency and relative phase are digitally adjusted in response to feedback signals provided by the Alfvén Eigenmode Local Manager (AELM) system. In this way, the phase of the feeding current to each antenna module can be independently adjusted [17]. In this paper we describe in greater detail the method presented in [17], to investigate the effectiveness of the phase adjustment scheme to improve the spectrum purity of the excited Alfvén Eigenmodes, through self-consistent numerical simulation employing the antenna version of the CASTOR code [20]. Specifically, the actual configuration of the new antenna system and the plasma response are both self-consistently included in the simulation. We show that, due to close spacing of the four modules in each of the two opposite antenna sectors, although the excitation of a mode with a specified value of n is favored by an optimal choice of the phases of the feeding currents, modes with nearby values of the toroidal mode number are also somewhat better excited.

In the following sections, we describe in detail the process of optimization of the antenna system, developed in [21] and briefly described in Section 3 of [17]. The configuration of the new antenna system is briefly discussed in the next section and then it is explained how it is modeled in the CASTOR code. The procedure followed to investigate the phase optimization is outlined in Section 3. The results of the application of this procedure to a well documented discharge of JET, shot # 77788 [18, 22], are then discussed in Section 4. In the Section 5 a proposal for a successful optimization is presented. Finally the conclusions are presented in Section 6.

2. Modeling the new antenna system in CASTOR

The antenna system of the AEAD is described in detail in references [9, 14-17, 22]. It consists basically of two units, each with four closely spaced rectangular coils with eighteen turns. The first turn is located approximately *45 mm* behind the poloidal limiter, the axis of the coils is perpendicular to magnetic surfaces, and their toroidal and poloidal lengths are *21 cm* and *23 cm*, respectively. The two units are placed in toroidally opposite positions, each one with a total length of approximately *130 cm*.

In the antenna version of the CASTOR code, the antenna current is modeled by a surface current density on a closed surface between the plasma boundary and the external wall, as specified in [17, 21]. Here, the vacuum solution for the excited magnetic field, obtained from the Laplace equation, is split into two main regions; one between the plasma and the antenna surface and the other between the antenna surface and the external wall. The proper boundary conditions are imposed at the interface between the plasma and the vacuum region, as also at the conducting wall; the jumping conditions at the antenna surface provide the driving term, which is associated with the antenna current [20].

As explained in [20, 21, 23, 17], each rectangular coil of the AEAD antenna system is represented by just a single rectangular coil, with the actual toroidal and poloidal lengths, centered at the radial and poloidal positions $(r_{\text{ant}}, \theta_{\text{ant}})$ and the effect of radial feeders are neglected. Under this condition, the surface current density in each poloidal strap k of a coil, centered at the coordinates $(r_{\text{ant}}, \theta_k, z_k)$, can be expanded in helical Fourier components:

$$j_k(\theta_k, z_k) = \sum_{m,n} j_{m,n}^k e^{i \left[m(\theta - \theta_k) + \frac{n}{R}(z - z_k) \right]} \quad (1)$$

where, in this case, $\theta_k = \theta_{\text{ant}}$ for all values of k . The values of the coefficients $j_{m,n}^k$ can be readily calculated for poloidal straps [24]. CASTOR code is run for each component individually, where the same component of the eight modules of the antenna were previously added up, so that the jump conditions can be unambiguously applied [20]. The eigenfunctions for each n component belonging to the excited spectrum are obtained by adding the results for the total of poloidal harmonics used in the calculations with the objective of limit computer time, the calculations were carried out with $|m| \leq 23$. For obtain our results presented in the sequel, were considering the values $r_{\text{ant}} = 1.3 \text{ m}$ and $\theta_{\text{ant}} = 0.08 \text{ rd}$.

3. Procedure for phase optimization of the feeding currents

In CASTOR, the phases of the feeding currents are specified to be only $(0, \pi)$. Therefore, the results of phase optimization cannot be directly computed. However, taking into account the helical Fourier representation of the current straps, the field components calculated for fixed mode numbers m and n , for an antenna module centered at (y_i, z_i) ; with $i = 1, 2, \dots, 8$, as indicated in the schematic cylindrical model of Fig.1, are simply related to those of a module centered at $(y=0, z=0)$ by the

phase coefficient $k_i = \exp[-i(m y_i/a + n z_i/R)]$, where a representing the plasma radius [17, 21]. We calculate the perturbed fields corresponding to all values of n of interest for each frequency ($1 \leq n \leq 17$ in the calculations presented in this work), for this we take into consideration the fact that one individual module can excite a large spectrum of n components. For each value of n , we calculated the real and imaginary parts of the radial component of the perturbed velocity, for all values of the poloidal components used to represent the eigenfunctions $|m| \leq 23$. With this values, we can reconstruct the same quantity for any other module using the corresponding phase coefficient, as well as, the amplitude and phase of the current feeding that module. Contour plot of the relative magnitude of the excited fields in the poloidal cross section plane, after all harmonics summation, is presented in Fig.2.

Fig. 1: Schematic cylindrical representation of the individual coil modules of the AEAD antenna.

Fig. 2: The contour plot of the magnitude of the excited fields in the JET poloidal cross section.

As described in [17, 21], in order to optimize the spectrum for a toroidal mode number n_0 , the phase of the current feeding the module located at z_i , considering as reference module $z_1=0$, has to be multiplied by the phase factor $\exp(-in_0z_i/R)$. This process maximizes the sum of the perturbed fields produced through all modules, at any radial position. However, the other components belonging to the same spectrum also will be multiplied by the factor $\exp[-i(n-n_0)z_i/R]$ and will interfere not in phase with the contributions from the other antenna modules. Therefore, the perturbed field distribution in a given poloidal plane will continue having components $n \neq n_0$ and, since for moderate values of this mode number ($n \geq 8$) the spectrum of TAEs is quasi degenerated, the eigenfunctions corresponding to satellite values of n can also be somewhat maximized. This effect is indeed verified in the results of the numerical simulations described in the sequel.

The vacuum spectrum of excited fields with $(0,0,0,0,\pi,\pi,\pi,\pi)$ phasing of eight JET antennas is

shown in Fig. 3(a). It is seen that the amplitudes of high n modes decrease rapidly with the growth of n and the maximum of the excited modes is grouped around $n=0$. When we introduce the phase shift ($\varphi_i=n_0z_i/R$); $|n_0|=9$ in the antenna feeding current, the maximum of the excited toroidal harmonics in the antenna spectrum is grouped around $n_0=-9$ (Fig. 3b), or $n_0=+9$ (Fig. 3c). It is seen that the phasing of antenna currents permits also to track the propagation of the TAE modes in toroidal direction.

Fig. 3: Spectrum of excited vacuum fields: (left) with $(0,0,0,0,\pi,\pi,\pi,\pi)$ antenna phasing, (center) with $\varphi_i=n_0z_i/R$ phasing, $n_0=-9$, (right) with $\varphi_i=n_0z_i/R$ phasing, $n_0=9$.

4. Results obtained with the phase optimization

In this section we describe the results of the described procedure to investigate the effect of phase optimization for the antenna of the AEAD system of JET. All the calculations were carried out for discharge #77788, which is a well-documented one of an experimental campaign to measure the damping rate of TAEs excited with the new antenna system, but with the antenna modules driven by just one RF amplifier [9, 18, 19, 22]. Actually, only four modules of antenna were employed with the phase configuration 1-/4-/6+/7+. Nevertheless, due to mutual coupling, current was also driven in other existing modules. Due to the chosen phasing to the four modules, even modes were not excited and an almost continuous $n=3$, $n=9$ and $n=11$ modes were observed.

In the simulations, after choosing the value of n , the spectrum of the excited modes is first calculated with all eight antenna modules using CASTOR directly, with odd phasing, i.e., modules 5 to 8 with opposite phase of modules 1 to 4. The necessary equilibrium quantities were obtained by equilibrium reconstruction at time $t=10$ s, using the HELENA code [25]. The corresponding safety factor profile is shown in Fig. 4(a). The plasma density profile, n_p , shown in Fig. 4(b), was adjusted from that presented in [26].

Knowing the safety factor profile, the expected range of frequencies for TAE modes can be estimated from the simple approximate expressions:

$$\frac{\omega}{V_A/R} = \frac{1}{2q(s)} \sqrt{\frac{n_{p0}}{n_{ps}}}; q(s) = \frac{m + \frac{1}{2}}{n}, \quad (2)$$

where V_A is the value of the Alfvén velocity at the plasma axis, n_{ps} is the density at the normalized radial coordinate s , and (m,n) is the pair of cylindrical mode numbers corresponding to the main gap in the Alfvén continuum [13].

Fig. 4: Safety factor radial profile reconstructed by HELENA for JET discharge # 77788 at $t=10$ s. (a) Density profile used in CASTOR to simulate the same discharge; $n_{p0} \approx 2.25 \times 10^{19} \text{ m}^{-3}$. (b) The coordinate s is the normalized radial coordinate employed in CASTOR [21, 26]. The plasma current is $I_p=2 \text{ MA}$ and the toroidal magnetic field $B_T=2.7 \text{ T}$.

As a control example, we take the $n=3$ mode, for which the TAE gap closest to the plasma axis occurs for $(m,m+1)=(3,4)$, at the magnetic surface $q(s)=1.167$. Based on the frequency estimation, we have carried out a gross frequency scan in the range $0.35 \leq x=Rw/V_A \leq 0.55$. The results are shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5: Absorbed power (arbitrary units) as a function of the normalized frequency for $n=3$ modes in JET, for the parameters of discharge # 77788 at $t=10$ s.

Three peaks are clearly observed in the absorbed power at $x=0.39$, 0.43 and 0.47 . The experimental values for the frequency are $f=186$, 179 and 174 kHz for $t = 9.3$, 13.8 and 14.9 s , respectively. Considering the values of the major radius, $R=2.96 \text{ m}$, and of the central plasma density, the frequency 186 kHz corresponds to $x=0.41$, therefore very close to the largest peak observed in Fig. 3. Actually, the difference between the experimental value and that of the

simulation corresponds to a relative error in the value of the central density $\delta n/nH 0.08$, well within the experimental error for the density measurement, and can also be due to uncertainties in the effective mass number, due to the presence of impurities like Be and W, because in this case the Alfvén velocity becomes $V_A=B/(\mu_0 \Sigma n_i m_i)^{1/2}$.

The radial profile of the absolute velocity of the radial component of the fluid velocity perturbation is shown in Fig. 6 for $x=0.43$, taking into account the contribution of the eight antenna modules. The red line corresponds to the contribution of all modes excited by the antennae and the asterisks to the $n=3$ mode only.

Fig. 6: Radial profile of the absolute value of the radial component of the perturbed velocity field (arbitrary units) excited by the external antennae driven at the normalized frequency $x=0.43$, for the parameters of discharge # 77788 at $t=10$ s. The feeding current of the eight antenna modules have all the same magnitude, 1 A, and phases $(0,0,0,0,\pi,\pi,\pi,\pi)$. The red line corresponds to the contributions of all modes and the asterisks to the $n=3$ mode only.

Fig. 7: Real (blue asterisks), imaginary (green broken line), and absolute (red solid line) radial profiles of the radial velocity field (arbitrary units) of the $n=3$ mode, for the same conditions of Fig. 6. In (a) the phases of the antenna modules are $(0,0,0,0,\pi,\pi,\pi,\pi)$, whereas in (b) they are optimized using the phase factor $\exp(-in_0 z_i/R)$, where $n_0=3$ and φ_i , $i=1, 2, \dots, 8$, determines to the toroidal position of each antenna module.

It is evident that, for this low value of n , the odd phasing of the two toroidally opposite antenna units already guarantees a reasonably pure spectrum. Indeed, if the optimization procedure is followed in this case, there is almost no change in the amplitude of the perturbation associated with the $n=3$ mode, as shown in Fig. 7. Actually, the relative change in the maximum of the absolute value is around 1.06.

The optimization procedure, however, has a small effect on the modes $n>3$. Looking in detail the behavior of the profile of the radial velocity field in Fig. 7, we see that the amplitude of the perturbation increases towards the plasma boundary, $s \square 1$ (red line). This is mostly due to the contribution of the $n=5$ mode. When the optimization procedure is carried out, the amplitude of this component increases by a factor of 1.15 close to the plasma boundary.

Let us now consider medium n modes. The normalized resonant frequencies obtained with CASTOR, using all antenna modules, with proper even or odd phasing of the two antenna units, are shown in Table 1. We see that the values of the normalized frequencies of the modes $n=9$ and $n=11$, for example, are almost degenerated. We then will explore the effect of the proper phase optimization on these modes, a somewhat more illustrative example.

n	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
x	0.38	0.51	0.49	0.53	0.48	0.43	0.55

Table 1: Values of the normalized frequency for the main Alfvén eigenmodes obtained with CASTOR for the parameters of JET discharge # 77788, at $t=10$ s [17, 21].

We first calculate the radial velocity fields for the frequencies corresponding to the two main $n=9$ and $n=11$ modes using $(0,0,0,0,\pi,\pi,\pi,\pi)$, which is the standard odd phasing of the two antenna units. The results of this process are shown in Fig. 8. It is observed that eigenfunctions of these modes are peaked approximately at plasma mid-radius and that many other modes also are excited by the antennae, particularly with large amplitudes close to the plasma boundary, which favors a better coupling with the antenna vacuum fields.

Fig. 8: Absolute value of the radial profile of the radial velocity field (arbitrary units) calculated with CASTOR for the normalized frequencies $x=0.49$, (a) corresponding to the eigenfrequency of the $n=9$ mode, and the $x=0.48$ [17, 21], (b) corresponding to the eigenfrequency of $n=11$ mode, excited by the external antenna system with $(0,0,0,0,\pi,\pi,\pi,\pi)$

phasing. The blue asterisks correspond to the eigenfunction of the corresponding main mode and the red line to the contributions of all modes excited by the antennae.

Let us now consider the effect of phase optimization. Applying the optimal phase factor $\exp(-in_0 z_i/R)$ to all antenna modules, we obtain the results shown in Fig. 9.

Fig. 9: Absolute value of the radial profile of the radial velocity field (arbitrary units) calculated with CASTOR for the normalized frequencies $x=0.49$, (a) corresponding to the eigenfrequency of the $n=9$ mode, and the $x=0.48$ [17, 21], (b) corresponding to the eigenfrequency of $n=11$ mode, excited by the external antenna system with optimal phasing $\exp(-in_0 z_i/R)$. The blue asterisks correspond to the eigenfunction of the corresponding main mode and the red line to the contributions of all modes excited by the antennae.

We see that with the optimization, the maximum amplitude of the main modes increase substantially, approximately doubling for the $n=9$ mode and increasing even more for the $n=11$ mode. However, the amplitudes of the other higher n modes also increase, although not as much as the main modes. This fact is due to the close spacing of the antenna modules in each unit, which make these modes quasi-degenerate and therefore does not allow good discrimination of the modes excited in the plasma and so the excitation can not be much optimized to select just one component. We hope in future works, to use these results to suggest analysis methods, even in real-time, so that the degeneracy of these modes can be resolved in the detection part of the diagnostic. We highlight that currently, real-time experiments are implemented taking into account the variation of other parameters besides the phase of the antennas, as well as the implementation of more sophisticated numerical codes that CASTOR code began to use [17, 27].

5. Proposal for a successful optimization using different antenna distribution in JET

According to our numerical results, the optimization is not entirely satisfactory to isolate successful only the central toroidal mode. The satellite modes are also better excited about the optimization process and their intensities are increased even in the biggest factors that the proper optimize mode, although it does not exceed the intensity of this. One possible cause could be due to

the symmetry and the proximity of the coils that make up the new JET antenna, which are not suitable for excitation of a satisfactorily pure spectrum. So, the effectiveness of using more antenna modules was also investigated, as also, their redefinition of locations around the plasma column. A possible configuration of antennae, with four modules, separated toroidally by $\pi/2$ and with each module consisting of eight square coils is sketched in Fig. 10.

The vacuum spectrum corresponding to the antenna configuration sketched in Fig. 10 is shown in Fig. 11, relating the absolute value of the total current density of the antenna for each toroidal mode with a particular combination of phase between the eight modules. It is clear that the optimization procedure isolates quite the desired toroidal mode, $n_0=9$, in this case.

Fig. 10: Proposal for the position of the antennas on the toroidal model.

Fig. 11: Vacuum spectrum for the antenna configuration with four modules (a) with unoptimized phases, i.e., phases $(0,0,0,0,\pi,\pi,\pi,\pi)$ for the coils in each module; (b) with of the phase of the feeding currents optimized to excite the $n_0 = 9$ mode.

The results considering the plasma response for the case $n_0=9$ are shown in Fig. 12. Without optimization of the phase of the feeding currents, i.e., phases $(0,0,0,0,\pi,\pi,\pi,\pi)$ for the coils in each module, there appears also many modes with $n \neq 9$ excited closer to the plasma boundary. With the proper optimization of the phases, according to Eq. (1), the amplitudes of these modes, relative to the amplitude of the main mode, are substantially reduced and the spectrum gets quite pure. Other configurations were also studied, for instance four modules separated by $\pi/2$, with four coils in each, and eight modules separated by $\pi/4$, also with four coils each. They all gave similar and satisfactory results.

Fig. 12: Spectrum the antenna configuration sketched in Fig. 10, including the self-consistent plasma response (a) with nonoptimized phases, i.e., phases $(0,0,0,0,\pi,\pi,\pi,\pi)$ for the coils in each module; (b) with of the phase of the feeding currents optimized to excite the $n_0 = 9$ mode.

6. Conclusions

The effect of feeding current optimization for the different modules of antenna the Alfvén Eigenmodes Active Diagnostic system of JET has been self consistently simulated using the antenna version of the CASTOR code [20]. Our results indicate that, although proper optimization indeed leads to an increase of the amplitude of the chosen mode, satellite modes with larger values of the toroidal mode numbers n can also increase amplitude, due to the quasi degeneracy of modes with $n \geq 9$ and the close spacing of the antenna modules.

We can conclude that the geometry of the current JET antenna it is not well suited for exciting a reasonable pure toroidal eigenmode. We have shown that this problem could be quite reasonably remediated by employing four antenna modules, separated toroidally by $\pi/2$. However, in case of JET, practical space limitations inside the vacuum vessel probably make this option almost impossible to implement. So, real-time experiments are at present implemented using the current antenna geometry. These experiments explore the variation of various parameters, not only of the phases of the currents, in order to identify the individual components of the excited spectrum [17, 27].

Acknowledgements

This work has been carried out under the Scientific Agreement for cooperation between the European Atomic Energy Community and the Government of the Federative Republic of Brazil in the field of fusion energy research and has been supported by the Brazilian agencies FAPESP, Project 2011/50773-0, and CNPq, Project 480733/2013-9.

We would especially like to thank Dr. Duarte Borba for the availability and support of the installation of CASTOR and Dr. Guido Huijsmans for his important support.

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